

HOW TO GET A BAND 9 OVERALL?

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of IELTS (International English Language Testing System) and how to get the highest score from it and it is going to be fully analyzed why it's global all around the world? Moreover, it includes much more information about niners (people who got 9 in overall) in Uzbekistan, their lifestyles and some of their quotes about studying.

Keyword: IELTS, highest score, global, niners, quotes, studying, personal lifestyles

КАК ПОЛУЧИТЬ ГРУППУ 9 В ЦЕЛОМ?

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена изучению IELTS (Международной системы тестирования английского языка) и тому, как получить по ней наивысший балл, и будет полностью проанализировано, почему она является глобальной по всему миру? Более того, он включает в себя гораздо больше информации о девятках (людях, набравших в общей сложности 9 баллов) в Узбекистане, их образе жизни и некоторых цитатах об учебе.

Ключевое слово: IELTS, наивысший балл, глобальный, девятки, цитаты, учеба, личный образ жизни.

INTRODUCTION

Originally launched in 1980, for more than 40 years IELTS has set the standard for English language testing to help people achieve their professional, personal, and academic ambitions.

Jointly owned by the British Council, IDP IELTS, and Cambridge University Press & Assessment – their combined global presence and commitment to research makes them ideal providers of international English testing.

MAIN PART

The British Council connects people worldwide with learning opportunities and creative ideas from the UK, and builds lasting relationships with other countries. The British Council is the UK's international organization for educational opportunity and cultural relations and is represented in over 140 countries worldwide.

IDP is a leader in global education services. As an Australian listed company, IDP operates in more than 50 countries and its websites attract 100 million visits a year. IDP specializes in combining human expertise with a leading digital platform to help people get accepted into their ideal course, take an English language test or learn English in their schools.

Cambridge English is part of the University of Cambridge. They develop and produce world-leading exams and tests for learners and teachers of English; 5.5 million of their assessments are taken every year in more than 130 countries. Around the world over 25,000 universities, employers, government ministries and other organisations rely on their exams and qualifications as proof of English language ability. Cambridge English exams are backed by over 100 years of expertise and experience in English language testing. Cambridge English is part of Cambridge University Press & Assessment-a not-for-profit organization.

In IELTS, there are different 4 categories: Listening, Reading, Writing and Speaking
Both Listening and Reading include 40 questions. Listening is divided into 4 sections while the Reading is consisted of 3 passages.

In Writing, there are given 2 tasks; Task1 and Task2. In writing task1 it should be written 150 words while In task 2 essay there should be 250 words

The Speaking is totally different, a real native speaker will be your examiner and she/he gives you some questions, it takes between 11 to 14 minutes and consists of 3 parts.

All IELTS scores are between 0 and 9. You can also get .5 scores as well (for example, 6,5 or 8,5). You will get a band score for each skill: Listening, Reading, Writing, Speaking and also an overall band score. The overall band score is the average score of all the skills.

For example: Listening 9 Reading 9 Writing 8.5 Speaking 9 Overall: $9+9+8.5+9=35.5$ $35.5/4=8.875 = 9$

Even though, it is very tough to get the maximum score in IELTS, some uzbek people proved that ‘Impossible is Possible’. In 2023, 3rd of March two uzbek people got 9 in overall with IDP, Muhammadali Sodikov the founder of ‘Ad Astra School’, and the founder of ‘IELTS Zone’ Bekzod Mirahmedov. They not only got the maximum score in IELTS but they also proved and opened new ways for the next, upcoming niners. After some time, the number of niners has increased significantly. Jakhongir Isomiddinov, Mamura Yuldasheva, Diyorbek Hayitmurodov, Dovudkhon Abdullayev and others got band 9 in overall and hopefully it will undoubtedly go on to increase day-by-day.

CONCLUSION

Muhammad Ali Sodikov is a really devoted person to IELTS. He gave up everything to get this band nine. As he broadcasted on the internet that he is not speaking uzbek anymore since 2019, wherever he goes and whatever he does he always speaks in English and he has already forgotten his own official language. He said that ‘The environment is a key’ You basically have to surround yourself with so much of the language and it is a natural approach.

And while he is taking the test, he always tells: ‘It’s not me, it’s my twin, quit chasing, we live in a simulation or something’.

‘You don’t get to live this life twice, I don’t know if there is a sequel but the only chance- ENJOY THE LIFE’.

REFERENCES

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